

Supplementary figures

High-throughput IgG Epitope mapping of Tetanus Neurotoxin: Implications for Immunotherapy and Vaccine Design

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Figure S1- List of TeNT (P01555), synthetic peptides and position in the cellulose membrane of Spot synthesis.

Figure S2- Mass spectrometry. The peptide 217 (MAP4-EKTLNDYKQFDSNG) was solubilized in deionized water to a final concentration of 10 µg/ml and then added formic acid to a final concentration of 0.1%. The mass spectrometer used was the Water UPLC model Acquity-I Class. The samples were electronically injected by the equipment at 1 µl/min. The range used for ion detection ranged from 1000-11500 m/z.